

Investigation of electron transfer properties of nitrogen-doped carbon dots obtained from a dialysis-free approach[†]

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Carbon dots (CDs) are widely used as a solar energy material in the current scenario. N-CDs-based dye sensitized solar cell (DSSC) device exhibited the best power conversion efficiency (PCE) so far. We hope a DSSC device based on covalently linked N-CDs with organic dyes may increase the efficiency of solar cells by blocking recombination effectively. As a preliminary study, before enter into the device fabrication, we have investigated the electron transfer behaviour of N-CDs in solution state in the presence of DMA and MV²⁺. We have synthesized the N-CDs from glycine by a simple dialysis-free approach. The resulting N-CDs exhibit luminescence quantum yield of 33.1%. The luminescence of N-CDs is effectively quenched by DMA and MV²⁺. Detailed investigation revealed that the quenching is caused by a dynamic photoinduced electron transfer mechanism and the bimolecular quenching constant values are $8.5 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $6.9 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively for DMA and MV²⁺.

Keywords: Glycine, donor-acceptor property, CDs stability, DSSCs, methyl viologen, dynamic quenching.

Introduction

Carbon dots (CDs), luminescent carbon nanoparticles of less than 10 nm size have subjected to a tremendous research since its accidental discovery in 2004 by Xu *et al.*¹. Their water solubility, luminescence, biocompatibility, tuneable emission, colloidal and luminescence stability in solution state, photostability, upconverted luminescence, immunity of luminescence to variable ionic strength and pH, environmental benign nature are some of their alluring properties which attracts the researchers to employ them in various fields of applications such as biosensing, chemical sensing, bioimaging, nanomedicine, electrocatalysis, supercapacitors, etc.²⁻⁸. On the other hand, their broad absorption spectra, large absorption coefficients⁹ and excellent solubility in polar solvents^{5,7} make them as the excellent alternatives to scant, costly, and toxic heavy metals¹⁰ commonly used for photovoltaic and photocatalytic applications.

Employing the CDs as a sensitizer and charge extracting agent is the recent trend in photovoltaic research¹¹. The CDs

have been employed as a constituent in dye sensitized solar cells (DSSCs), Perovskite-based solar cells, polymer-based organic solar cells, quantum dot sensitized solar cells, silicon-based solar cells, and small molecule organic solar cells¹¹. Much works have been done on CDs-based DSSCs over other solar cells. In most of the CDs-based DSSCs, the CDs are employed as the sensitizer¹²⁻¹⁶. However, the power conversion efficiency (PCE) looks poor. Ma *et al.* has reported¹⁷ a different approach of making CDs-Rhodamine B mixture as the sensitizer. They found that the dual function of CDs as donor and acceptor of electrons efficiently blocks the recombination of photogenerated carriers and increases the PCE to about 7-folds compared to the non-CDs analogue. Moreover, the CDs absorbing the incident photons in addition with the organic dye sensitizer which extends the overall absorbing region of the DSSC device. Another different approach is reported¹⁸ by Shen *et al.* who employed the reaction mixture containing CDs in its precursor plant extract as the sensitizer and achieved the PCE of up to 0.48%. Wang

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*et al.*¹⁹ has revealed that nitrogen-doped carbon dots (N-CDs) exhibits about 0.79% of PCE which is several folds higher than the previously reported CDs-sensitized solar cells. From these background studies, it is clear that the N-CDs and CDs with an organic dye sensitizer exhibits superior PCE compared with mere CDs-sensitized solar cells. We hope if we covalently link the N-CDs with the organic dye instead of making mere CDs-Dye mixtures, the PCE may be improved to a significant extent.

To link the N-CDs with semiconductor (such as TiO₂) and the organic dye, it should possess both the amine and carboxylic acid functional groups. The amine functional group of N-CDs may be coupled with many commercial dye sensitizers as the sensitizers possess carboxylic acid functional groups in order to bind on the semiconductor surface. On the other hand, the carboxylic acid functionality of the N-CDs may be adsorbed physically or chemically on the semiconductor surface. The immediate precursors that we can think for the synthesis of amine and carboxylic acid functionalized N-CDs are amino acids which have been used by many researchers as the precursor for the synthesis of N-CDs²⁰.

In this context, we have synthesized highly luminescent N-CDs from glycine, simplest amino acid. Hsu *et al.* have already reported²¹ the synthesis of N-CDs from glycine by adopting hydrothermal carbonization method. Our synthetic method differs from that of Hsu's method in terms of synthetic conditions and the method of purification. Most importantly, we have avoided the use of dialysis membrane which is expensive and the dialysis process is time consuming. We improved the production yield and luminescence quantum yield of N-CDs by changing the reaction conditions. Consequently, the obtained N-CDs exhibits different structural and optical behaviours compared with the one reported by Hsu *et al.* Before employing these N-CDs in light harvesting and similar applications, it is important to investigate its electron transfer properties in solution state.

The photoinduced electron transfer properties may offer new opportunities in potentially exploiting CDs for light energy conversion and related applications, in addition to their being valuable to the effort on mechanistic elucidation. The Sun research group²² have revealed that the CDs are behaving as electron transfer agents. However, it need not be true for all the CDs and needs experimental verification for

the particular CDs. In this context, we have studied the electron transfer properties of the amine and carboxylic acid co-functionalized N-CDs by taking N,N-dimethyl aniline (DMA) as the electron donor and methyl viologen dichloride (MV²⁺) as electron acceptor. The oxidation potential of DMA (1.23 V vs NHE) is comparable with that of organic dye sensitizers while the reduction potential of MV²⁺ (-0.44 V vs NHE) is close to the conduction band (CB) potential of TiO₂ (-0.5 V vs NHE). We have thoroughly investigated the electron transfer behaviour of the bifunctional N-CDs and confirmed the photoinduced electron transfer process from N-CDs to MV²⁺ and DMA to N-CDs.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of luminescent N-CDs

The synthetic procedure of N-CDs is elaborated in the supporting information. After the hydrothermal carbonization of glycine, the final aqueous solution is converted to ethanolic solution and kept in a freezer for about 4 h. As the glycine is insoluble in ethanol, if there is any unreacted glycine, it will be precipitated in ethanol. The low temperature ambient can assist the rapid precipitation process. The unreacted glycine alone is not the impurity. Yang and co-workers²³ revealed that the organic fluorophores that formed due to partial carbonization of the starting material exhibits up to 90% luminescence quantum yield (QY). In fact, the PL of some CDs may be dominated by the molecular state, in which a PL centre is formed solely by an organic fluorophore²⁴. Thus, it is difficult to explain the specific chemical structure of CDs and the components contributing to PL. Moreover, there is a good possibility to get incorrect luminescence quantum yield values due to the interference of these fluorescent, partially carbonized fragments. Hence, it is essential to ensure that the partially carbonized species were removed completely prior to characterization and photophysical studies. During the carbonization process, some hydrophobicity is incorporated into the starting material glycine so that the resulting N-CDs are soluble in ethanol (less polar compared with water), whereas the glycine is insoluble in it. Hence, the partially carbonized products and the fragments formed on the beginning of carbonization but failed to involve in carbonization, which exhibits similar solubility as glycine i.e. they are insoluble in ethanol. Therefore, on freezing, we were able to remove these interferers too together with the unreacted glycine. The Scheme S1 and S2 in Supplementary data illus-

trates the synthetic procedure and the science behind the purification process respectively. The UV-Vis absorption spectrum (Fig. 4a) of our N-CDs (final centrifugate) shows no background absorbance in the visible region indicates the absence of other carbonaceous materials resulting from partial carbonization which usually absorb at longer wavelengths. Moreover, we didn't notice any difference between the UV-Vis absorption spectra of our N-CDs solution before and after dialysis for 12 h using a cellulose ester dialysis membrane (Spectra/Por, Float-A-Lyzer G2, 1 KD MWCO), purchased from Spectrum Labs. Therefore, our synthetic method eliminates the dialysis step which is a time consuming purification method. Besides that the dialysis membranes are expensive and in some cases leaching out of CDs from the dialysis membrane was observed²⁵. We have observed that the leaching out issue is more pronounced when the dialysis period extends more than 8 h. The prolonged dialysis causes the dialysis tube to swell which may introduce strain on the membrane leading to enlarged pore diameter. As the consequence, the CDs may escape from the dialysis tube which would reduce the production yield of CDs. Table S1 in the Supplementary data compares the luminescence quantum yields and production yields of N-CDs obtained by common dialysis approach and our dialysis-free approach. In our approach, both the luminescence and production yields are higher. Hence, in this work, we improved the method of production of N-CDs by optimizing the reaction condition, modified purification process, and by choosing an efficient precursor. The N-CDs display wonderful solubility in many polar solvents such as H₂O, lower alcohols, (CH₃)₂CO, (CH₃)₂NCHO and in (CH₃)₂SO. Its marvellous solubility in polar solvents supposes that the N-CDs are swaddled by a plenty of polar surface functionalities.

Interestingly, the white solid obtained on freezing, are brightly fluorescent, and the fluorescence exhibits excitation wavelength dependency (Supplementary data, Fig. S1). Any one or both the two possibilities, that are listed below can be the reasons for the observed fluorescence from the white precipitate: (1) partially carbonized polymer-like fluorescent fragments with different degree of polymerization, (2) trapping of fluorescent N-CDs into the precipitated starting material or/and into the precipitated partially carbonized fragments (Usually, N-CDs are non fluorescent in their solid state due to aggregation but they retain their fluorescence when

they are trapped into a salt matrix such as sodium sulphate²⁶ and potash alum²⁷).

Characterization

The size distribution and morphology of N-CDs were characterized by TEM (Fig. 1a). As shown in Fig. 1a, the as prepared N-CDs are monodispersed, quasispherical and are well separated from each other. The histogram in Fig. 1b shows the corresponding size distribution of CDs. The statistical diameter of the N-CDs is 2.7 ± 0.72 nm on analyzing about 50 particles as shown in Fig. 1b. An X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of N-CDs (Fig. 1c) showed a single broad peak centred at $2\theta = 24.8^\circ$, which is consistent with the (002) lattice spacing of carbon-based materials with profuse sp³ disorder. The interlayer spacing is 3.6 Å, larger than that of bulk graphite (3.3 Å), indicating a poor crystallization. The selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern (inset of Fig. 1a) of N-CDs is in well agreement with these results. Hence, the amorphous nature of N-CDs is confirmed by the obtained XRD and SAED patterns. In Fig. 1d, the Raman spectrum of the carbon dots exhibits two peaks at 1352 and 1565 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the D and G bands of carbon, respectively. The D band is associated with the vibrations of carbon atoms with dangling bonds in the termination plane of disordered graphite or glassy carbon. The G band corresponds to the E_{2g} mode of the graphite and is related to the vibration of sp²-bonded carbon atoms in a two-dimensional (2D) hexagonal lattice. The ratio of I_D/I_G is 1.31, which is characteristic of the disorder extent and the ratio of sp³/sp² carbon, implying that there is a plenty of structural defects in the N-CDs. The XPS survey spectrum in Fig. 2a, reveals that the N-CDs are composed of carbon (71.4%), oxygen (21.9%), and nitrogen (6.7%). The C 1s (Fig. 2b), O 1s (Fig. 2c), and N 1s (Fig. 2d) spectra were deconvoluted into four, two, and two constituent peaks respectively. The peaks at 285.2 eV and 288.5 eV in C 1s spectrum and at 530.5 eV and 533 eV in O 1s spectrum were attributed to the presence of carboxylic acid functional groups on the surface of N-CDs. Similarly, the peaks at 285.2 eV in C 1s spectrum and at 401.6 eV and 400.4 eV in N 1s spectrum were assigned to the amine functional groups on the surface. The presence of sp³ C-C/sp² C=C at 284.7 eV was observed in the C 1s spectrum of our N-CDs. We have recorded FTIR spectrum (Fig. 3) for the N-CDs to identify its surface functionalities. A broad absorption from 3700 to 3300 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the collective ab-

Fig. 1. (a) TEM image of N-CDs (inset: SAED pattern), (b) Particle size distribution of N-CDs, (c) XRD pattern of N-CDs, (d) Confocal Raman spectrum of N-CDs.

sorption of O-H and N-H stretching frequencies. Sharp and strong absorptions at 1634 cm^{-1} and 1385 cm^{-1} are attributed to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of carboxylic acid functionality. Peaks at 1465 cm^{-1} and 1532 cm^{-1} are assigned to the C-N stretching vibration and bending vibration of protonated amines respectively. Finally, the carbonization peak has appeared at about 575 cm^{-1} . A negative apparent zeta potential value (Supplementary data, Fig. S2) of $-14.1 \pm 6.11\text{ mV}$ reveals that the net charge on the surface of the N-CDs is negative. From the zeta potential, it is envisaged that the N-CDs are primarily functionalized by carboxylic acid functional groups rather than amine functional groups even though the starting material containing equal number of carboxylic acid and amine functional groups. It portrays that the loss of amine functionality dominates the loss of carboxylic acid functional group during the high pressure pyrolysis treatment. Hence, we envision logically that

all the amine groups will be neutralized by nearby carboxylic acid groups so that the ultimate functionalities on the surface of the N-CDs are protonated amine, deprotonated carboxylic acid, and unionised carboxylic acid. It should be noted here that the zeta potential accounts only for the net charge on the surface of a nanoparticle. Some of the positively charged amines are neutralized by the equal number of negatively charged carboxylic acids that are not included in the given net zeta potential. Hence, the actual charge on the surface of our N-CDs should be higher.

Optical properties of N-CDs

The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of the N-CDs is shown in the Fig. 4a. The absorption spectrum exhibits two peaks around 265 and 325 nm and extends to 500 nm without noticeable structures. According to previous studies²⁸, the peak at 265 nm is ascribed to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition of aromatic C=C

Fig. 2. (a) XPS survey spectrum, and high resolution, (b) C 1s, (c) O 1s, (d) N 1s spectra of N-CDs.

Fig. 3. FTIR spectrum of N-CDs.

bonds, while a shoulder at 325 nm attributes to $n-\pi^*$ transition of C=O bonds. C=O groups may originate from the surface of CDs, while C=C from the core. As shown in the inset of Fig. 4a, the N-CDs display relatively strong blue luminescence under UV irradiation ($\lambda = 365$ nm). In accordance with

most luminescent carbon nanoparticles, these N-CDs also exhibit excitation-dependent photoluminescence (PL) behaviour (Fig. 4b). The PL peak maximum is observed at 423 nm when excited at 340 nm. An apparent red shift is observed in the corresponding normalized emission spectrum (Supplementary data, Fig. S3) while increase the excitation wavelengths. The quantum yield of the N-CDs is about 33.1% (Supplementary data, Fig. S4 and Table S2 and S3) in comparison with quinine sulfate (QY 0.54 in 0.1 NH_2SO_4). The PL decay analysis is performed to measure the lifetime of the N-CDs. The lifetime data of N-CDs were very well fitted to a tri-exponential function as shown in Fig. 4c and Fig. S6 (Supplementary data). The parameters generated from iterative deconvolution of the decay with the instrument response function (IRF) are listed in the Table S4 of Supplementary data. The observed lifetimes of the N-CDs are $\tau_1 = 0.72$ ns, $\tau_2 = 3.21$ ns, and $\tau_3 = 8.22$ ns, and the calculated average lifetime, τ_{avg} is 5.75 ns. The observed nanosecond lifetime suggests that the as prepared N-CDs are most suitable for optoelectronic and biological applications²⁹.

Fig. 4. (a) UV-Vis absorption spectra of N-CDs and glycine (inset: photographs of N-CDs solution at day light and UV light), (b) PL spectra of N-CDs at various excitation wavelengths, (c) PL decay of N-CDs.

Stability of N-CDs

The N-CDs solution displays a long-term homogeneous phase without any conspicuous precipitation at room temperature. In addition, the luminescence intensity has no perceptible change during long-term storage for 120 days (Fig. 5a). The influence of pH change on the luminescence of N-CDs is analyzed by monitoring the luminescence intensity at various pH (Fig. 5b). The luminescence of the N-CDs is not radically affected on a broad range of pH (from pH 2 to pH 12). It is interesting to note that the mean luminescence lifetime of the N-CDs also not affected much on a broad pH range (Supplementary data, Fig. S7a and S7b and Table S5). In addition, the luminescence is almost unaffected over a broad range of ionic strength, from 0 M to 2 M as shown in the Fig. 5c. The luminescence stability of the N-CDs can be correlated with their surface morphological stability since the luminescence of the N-CDs is mainly originated from their surface functional groups (Supplementary data, Fig. S5). Hence, the stability of our N-CDs at various pH and ionic strengths upholds our N-CDs as the effective candidate for DSSC applications in which the N-CDs have to be sandwiched between conductive plates with redox electrolytes on device fabrication. Apart from the stabilities under various pH and ionic strengths, it is more important to investigate the photo and thermal stabilities of the N-CDs in order to understand their suitability to be tough enough to resist degradation on solar irradiation. In this perspective, the N-CDs are subjected to UV irradiation for 70 min using a 365 nm UV lamp to investigate its photostability. It is found from Fig. 5d that the N-CDs exhibit an excellent photostability which is quite better than that of rhodamine 6G (Rh6G) which is a commercial dye for bioimaging and one of the sensitizers

reported for DSSC application³⁰⁻³². The thermal stability of N-CDs is investigated in the range of temperatures 30–80°C. The luminescence of N-CDs found to be decreases upon increasing the temperature (Supplementary data, Fig. S8a) which is due to the thermally activated non-radiative trapping. The probability for thermal activation of non-radiative channels in low temperature is very low³³. When increasing the temperature, the non-radiative channels become activated resulting in the lowering of QY. The decrease of non-radiative lifetime with increasing temperature can be expressed mathematically using eq. (1)³⁵:

$$\tau_{NR} = \tau_0 e^{E_a/k_B T} \quad (1)$$

where, E_a denotes activation energy, k_B is the Boltzmann constant. The luminescence is very slightly affected with time even at high temperature, 343 K (Supplementary data, Fig. S8b). This kind of weak temperature effect in N-CDs is consistent with the fact that the dominant interaction mechanism involves electron-electron interactions rather than electron-phonon coupling³⁴.

Apart from photovoltaic applications, these N-CDs may also be used as fluorescence probes for biological applications due to their pH, ionic strength, and photostabilities. Hence, we were curious to investigate its cytotoxic nature and we found that the N-CDs exhibits excellent cell viability towards A549 cells (Supplementary data, Fig. S9). Further discussion about the cell viability of N-CDs is presented in the supporting information. All these results representing that our N-CDs are appropriate for solution state studies, photovoltaics and biomedical applications.

N-CDs as electron donor-acceptor material

The donor-acceptor behaviour of N-CDs is investigated

Fig. 5. (a) Long-term luminescence stability of N-CDs. Effect of (b) pH, (c) ionic strength and (d) UV irradiation on the luminescence intensity of N-CDs.

by employing DMA as electron donor (N-CDs as electron acceptor) and MV^{2+} as electron acceptor (N-CDs as electron donor). The UV-Vis absorption spectra of N-CDs in the presence of various concentrations of DMA and MV^{2+} were shown in the Fig. S10a and S10b (Supplementary data). The corresponding PL spectra (Fig. 6a and 6b) exhibit a regular and linear PL quenching of N-CDs on addition of the quenchers (DMA or MV^{2+}). The observed quenching may be either due to energy transfer or electron transfer. However, the energy transfer mechanism is not feasible in this case due to the poor overlap between the PL spectrum of N-CDs and the absorption spectra of DMA and MV^{2+} (Supplementary data, Fig. S11). The other possibility, electron transfer mechanism can be operated through static or dynamic pathways. The static quenching is often observed as a result of ground state complex formation between the fluorophore and the quencher. To find out the contribution of any ground state

complex formation, we have compared the absorption spectra of N-CDs in the presence of quenchers (DMA or MV^{2+}) with the arithmetic addition of absorbance of N-CDs and the quenchers (Supplementary data, Fig. S12a and S12b). Only a very small difference between the two spectra shows no or only a slight static contribution should be there to the overall quenching process. To gain further insight on the nature of quenching, we have performed Stern-Volmer analysis for the quenching of N-CDs in the presence of DMA and MV^{2+} . The so called Stern-Volmer equation is given below (eq. (2)).

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_{SV} [Q] \quad (2)$$

where, F_0 and F are the PL intensities of N-CDs in the absence and presence of quencher, respectively. K_{SV} is the Stern-Volmer quenching constant, $[Q]$ is the concentration of quencher. The plot of F_0/F vs $[Q]$ exhibits a good linear

Fig. 6. Quenching of N-CDs PL on increasing the concentration of (a) DMA, (b) MV^{2+} .

correlation as shown in Fig. 7a and 7b. The slope of the plot is nothing but K_{SV} , which is $35.1 \pm 0.5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ for DMA and $27.1 \pm 0.5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ for MV^{2+} . The excellent linear correlation reveals that the observed fluorescence quenching is either cent percent static or cent percent dynamic and not the static-dynamic combination in which the correlation will exhibit a concave upward deviation³⁵. The magnitude of bimolecular quenching constant will provide more information on the nature of quenching compared with the Stern-Volmer quenching constant. The relationship between these two constants is given below (eq. (3)).

$$K_{SV} = k_q \tau_0 \quad (3)$$

where, k_q is the bimolecular quenching constant and τ_0 is the average luminescence lifetime of N-CDs in the absence of quencher. The k_q is calculated to be $9.1 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and

$6.9 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively for the quenching of N-CDs luminescence by DMA and MV^{2+} . Both the values are very close to the diffusion-controlled rate constant which is $10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, suggesting a dynamic electron transfer mechanism. In principle, fluorescence lifetime measurement is the most definitive method to distinguish between the static and dynamic quenching processes. In this context, we have done fluorescence lifetime quenching analysis to confirm the nature of quenching. Fig. 8a and 8b shows the response of PL decay curves on the addition of DMA and MV^{2+} respectively. The PL decay curves exhibit a regular and linear quenching of N-CDs luminescence lifetime on addition of the quenchers (DMA or MV^{2+}). The corresponding K_{SV} and k_q values are obtained by plotting τ_0/τ against the $[Q]$ according to the Stern-Volmer equation (Fig. 8c and 8d) for lifetime quench-

Fig. 7. Stern-Volmer plots for the PL quenching of N-CDs on increasing the concentration of (a) DMA, (b) MV^{2+} .

Fig. 8. PL decay profiles of N-CDs on increasing the concentrations of (a) DMA, (b) MV²⁺ and Stern-Volmer plots for the quenching of N-CDs PL lifetime on increasing the concentrations of (c) DMA, (d) MV²⁺.

ing which is shown below (eq. (4)).

$$\tau_0/\tau = 1 + K_{SV} [Q] = 1 + k_q \tau_0 [Q] \quad (4)$$

where, τ_0 and τ are the lifetimes of N-CDs, in the absence and in the presence of quencher respectively. The K_{SV} values obtained for the N-CDs lifetime quenching by DMA and MV²⁺ are $33.2 \pm 1.7 \text{ M}^{-1}$, $26.9 \pm 1.3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ respectively. The corresponding bimolecular quenching constants are $8.5 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $6.9 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. Both the K_{SV} and k_q values are in excellent agreement with those derived from luminescence quenching. Hence, the dynamic electron transfer process is confirmed without further questions.

Conclusions

Highly luminescent, amine and carboxylic acid co-functionalized N-CDs have been synthesized by a dialysis-

free approach and without the aid of any passivating agent. The N-CDs exhibits excellent colloidal and luminescence stability under various conditions in solution state. The remarkable photo and thermal stabilities of the N-CDs makes them as an excellent candidate for photovoltaic application. The bifunctional nature of the N-CDs may be exploited to covalently link them between semiconductor surface and the sensitizer which may enhance the efficiency of dye sensitized solar cells by blocking the electron recombination between the conduction band (CB) of semiconductor and the oxidized sensitizer. In this context, the electron transfer properties of N-CDs have been studied and it is revealed that the N-CDs exchanges photoelectrons between DMA (Dye analogue) and MV²⁺ (TiO₂ analogue) thereby behaving as both electron donor and acceptor. N-CDs in its reduced form (by accepting electrons from the sensitizer) may efficiently trans-

fer the electron to the CB of TiO₂ compared to its neutral form and as the consequence, the N-CDs may effectively block the recombination process. We hope this investigation will be helpful in light-harvesting and related applications. Efforts to fabricate a DSSC device based on this idea are underway in our laboratory.

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